

اسلام میں عیدین کی اہمیت و فضیلت، علمی و تحقیقی جائزہ

The significance and virtues of the two Eids in Islam: A scholarly and research-based analysis.

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Abstract

Festival celebrations are a common phenomenon in every culture, representing certain cultural, social, and communal aspects of society. However, Islamic culture associates celebrations with religious values and introduces two official festivals, Eid-ul-Fitr and Eid-ul-Adha, in the lunar Islamic calendar. Muslims celebrate Eid al-Fitr at the end of the month of Ramadan, while Eid al-Adha is celebrated on the tenth of the month of Dhu al-Hijja. These two festivals do not mark any historical events; rather, they encourage Muslim societies and individuals to offer thanks to Allah Almighty and to demonstrate mercy, compassion, and sympathy for those who are less privileged. This article is an attempt to explore the spiritual message enshrined in the Islamic philosophy of celebrating Eid. The article also provides a detailed review of the related Quranic verses, Prophetic narrations, and Islamic jurisprudence.

Keywords: Eid's In Islam, Significance, Festival Celebration, Official Festivals, Ramadan

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Journal of Quranic
and Social Studies

59-70

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Volume:3, Issue:2, 2023

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.

www.jqss.org

ISSN: E/ 2790-5640

ISSN: P/ 2790-5632

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